

Chronopolitics in Counter-Revolutionary Tunisia

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What does investigating the politics of time contribute to our understanding of political dynamics in re-autocratizing Tunisia? The literature on authoritarian resilience and democratic backsliding in the region (Lynch, Schwedler, and Yom 2022; Ridge 2022, Sadiki and Saleh 2023; Rivera-Escartin 2024) provides ample theoretical arguments and empirical evidence regarding how legal structures, institutional configurations, international alliances, and popular discontent have contributed to Kais Saied's authoritarian restoration. Yet, problematizing the politics of time as a mechanism of authoritarian reproduction can provide new insights into the dynamics shaping counter-revolutionary Tunisia. More precisely, investigating the chronopolitics of Saied's authoritarianism sheds light on how the control of political time and temporal imaginaries create structures that reinforce autocratic outcomes.

The concept of chronopolitics explores how the control of time in its manifest sense and through hegemonic narratives of the past, present, and future serve as tools of power exertion and legitimation (Clark 2019). Chronopolitics can be observed in the utilization of time for the structuring of quotidian life, in the temporal defining of political instances (the "time of politics"), and in the politicization of temporalities for specific political

purposes (Esposito and Baker 2023). In the case of Tunisia, Kais Saied's manipulation of the time of politics along with his politicization of temporalities and the meanings attributed to the past, present, and future serve as tools to diffuse opposition and produce discursive incongruity with the counter-revolutionary nature of his political project. In one vein, Kais Saied's temporal management of the rhythm and predictability of political instances has been utilized as part of a broader effort to organizationally scramble the possibility of mounting a viable opposition force. After suspending the 2014 constitution, Saied presented his new draft version only three weeks before the scheduled July 2022 referendum, providing nearly no time for the opposition to strategize or for debate to exist in the public sphere. In March 2023 he dissolved the municipal councils several months before the scheduled elections, to then announce in September that elections for local councils – institutional bodies unforeseen in the new constitution – would be held only three months later. Likewise, his announcement in July 2024 of the calendar for presidential elections left potential candidates with only weeks to meet the onerous threshold for signatures. While this is not to imply that the temporal management of political procedures since 2021 is the primary reason Saied has been able to concretize his autocratic turn, investigating the politics of time elucidates

autocratic strategies that diminish the organizational capacity for democratic resistance.

In another vein, the temporal imaginaries of the past, present, and future imbued in Saied's rhetoric contribute to a justification of his political methods while presenting a double-speak regarding the nature of his rule. With regards to the past, Saied presents a historical interpretation of the near past that entirely delegitimizes the decade of democratic transition. He describes the years following the 2011 uprising as not only chaotic and destabilizing but as an accident of history and aberration of the country's natural political order (Geisser 2023). Instead, Saied puts forth an interpretation of Tunisian history that traces the uniqueness of the country's political trajectory and the singularity of its national identity. This includes the uniqueness of the 2011 revolution, which he sets apart from the other Arab uprising of 2011 (Rahmouni 2023), but also the unparalleled will of the Tunisian nation to confront threats across history. This imaginary of the past conjures that of a nation facing repeated challenges to its independence and identity, in which it is the "people" that have resisted and risen above. This framing forms an essential dimension to Saied's brand of populism and his discourse on the defense of the nation and the re-establishment of popular sovereignty. It also underscores how the present is framed and managed.

Indeed, Saied's conspiratorial populism (Annovi 2024) hinges upon an imaginary of the present framed within a historical continuity of threat emanating from both outside and within, which he institutionalizes in the perpetual state of emergency. His narrative of Tunisia's distant and near past serves as the parameters to define the "we" of the polity and the "enemy" of the country's

political project, fueling his rhetoric of existential threat. This includes the inscribing of sub-Saharan migration as a threat to Tunisian national identity and the defining of former political elites and oppositional voices as traitors to the revolution's quest for popular sovereignty. In framing the present as a moment of acute crisis, Saied is able to repeatedly justify the renewal of the country's state of emergency (a strategy typical among the region's autocrats), thus also stretching out the temporality of the present. In this way, the fulfillment of the vision for the future he claims to be solely capable of achieving – based on economic prosperity and a renewal of democracy via the restoration of popular will as the cornerstone of governance – is perpetually delayed.

This temporal distancing of the future through the permanent liminality of the present contributes to autocratic reproduction in two important ways. First, the state of emergency not only provides extraordinary powers of repression in a context of constitutional extra-legality but also allows him to discursively distance himself from the autocratic nature of his political practice in the guise of temporal exceptionality. In this way, he is able to repeatedly claim to be re-establishing the revolutionary demand for popular sovereignty while nonetheless exercising a form of power where the people are "conspicuously absent" (Lakhal 2022). Second, the perpetuity of the exceptional period of crisis produces what Hage (2009) calls "stuckedness," a state that must be coped with and waited out rather than acted upon, thereby generating political ambivalence and self-restraint. This unbounded nature of the present and its politicization as a time of crisis also serves to stifle future imaginaries through the fostering of despair. Consequently, as contemporary theories of time argue, the way the future is

expected, projected, and inhabited has a direct impact on the nature of political action (Bazzani 2023).

In focus groups conducted with young people from Tunisia's marginalized interior and peri-urban regions in 2021 and then again in 2023, my co-investigators and I were able to trace how Saïed's politics of time has reshaped youth imaginaries of the past and future and their ensuing propensity for political action (Jmal and Lakhali 2024). In just two years, there was a simultaneous rise in authoritarian nostalgia and a fall in the sense of agency over the country's ambiguous and out-of-grasp future. These temporal understandings in turn informed their modes of action. Across the focus groups, youth spoke of divestment from the collective as a sphere of action in favor of self-optimization strategies. In this way, Saïed's politics of time is contributing to popular legitimation around the idea of strong-man rule, but also a broader process of demobilization and disengagement from collective action and political life. That being said, the perpetual delay of his vision for the future has also led to increasing frustration with the president himself. Moving forward, a research agenda that centrally considers the politics of time in today's Tunisia could reveal how the construction, narration, and manipulation of temporalities and temporal rhythms act as institutional and cognitive regulators that facilitate authoritarian reproduction. Perhaps, such research could also explore how alternative future imaginaries could carve out spaces and modalities for democratic resilience via a prefigurative future-making process of resistance. ♦

References

- Annovi, Claudia. 2024. "Exploring Conspiracist Populism in Power: The Case of Kais Saïed in Tunisia." *Genealogy* 8(2): 43.
- Bazzani, Giacomo. 2023. "Futures in Action: Expectations, Imaginaries and Narratives of the Future." *Sociology* 57(2): 382–97.
- Clark, Christopher. 2019. *Time and Power*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Esposito, Fernando, and Tobias Becker. 2023. "The Time of Politics, the Politics of Time, and Politicized Time: An Introduction to Chronopolitics." *History and Theory* 62(4): 3–23.
- Geisser, Vincent. 2023. "La Tunisie de Kaïs Saïed: Héritage Révolutionnaire et Restauration Autoritaire." *Diplomatie: affaires stratégiques et relations internationales* 118.
- Hage, Ghassan. 2009. "Waiting Out the Crisis: On Stuckedness and Governmentality." In *Waiting*, ed. Ghassan Hage, 97–106. Melbourne: Melbourne University Press.
- Jmal, Nadia, and Malek Lakhali. 2024. "Tunisian Youth Perceptions of Authoritarian Restoration: Withering Support to Democracy." *Arab Reform Initiative*. <https://www.arab-reform.net/publication/tunisian-youth-perceptions-of-authoritarian-restoration-withering-support-to-democracy/>.
- Lakhali, Malek. 2022. "The Ghost People and Populism from Above: The Kais Saïed Case." *Arab Reform Initiative*. <https://www.arab-reform.net/publication/the-ghost-people-and-populism-from-above-the-kais-saied-case/>

Lynch, Marc, Jillian Schwedler, and Sean Yom. 2022. *The Political Science of the Middle East: Theory and Research since the Arab Uprisings*. Oxford University Press.

Rahmouni, Kamilia. 2023. "Language, Power and Identity: Discursive Construction of Post-Revolution National Identity in Tunisia." *Critical Discourse Studies* 20(6): 683–99.

Ridge, Hannah M. 2022. "Dismantling New Democracies: The Case of Tunisia." *Democratization* 29(8): 1539–56.

Rivera-Escartin, Adrià. 2024. "Elite Polarization and Democratic Backsliding in Tunisia: Tracing Agency-Driven Mechanisms." *Democratization* 31(4): 871–90.

Sadiki, Larbi, and Layla Saleh, eds. 2023. "A Case of Democratic Degeneration? Towards Critical Democratisation in MENA" [Special Issue]. *Journal of North African Studies* 23(6).